

**TOBACCO THIRPS IN COTTON AND PESTICIDES TO CONTROL THEM
BIOLOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS**

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Abstract. *The article contains information about the spread of tobacco thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lind) in cotton, its damage and measures to combat it. ..., Benzophosphate 30% n.kuk. used against tobacco thrips the biological effectiveness of drugs has been studied. Forms, methods of use and standards of drugs are shown in a scientifically based way.*

Keywords: *factors, pesticide, pest, chemical control, drugs, efficiency, yield.*

Cotton is one of the crops that are often damaged by pests. Professor V.V. Yakhontov compiled a list of the world fauna of 772 species of invertebrates feeding on cotton and described it as early as 1931. Of these, 751 species belong to the class of insects. A. I. Petrov identified 219 types of pests in cotton. A very few of these species - about 10 species - cause serious damage to cotton. But those that rank second in terms of harmfulness can cause significant damage to cotton when the conditions are favorable. Depending on the method of nutrition, pests can be divided into groups of suckers and rodents.

Tobacco thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lind) is a serious pest of agricultural crops, and during April and May it causes great economic damage to cotton and other agricultural crops. Damaged cotton remains from the plant. Even the upper part of the seed coat is damaged when the number of the pest increases and it is severely damaged. Tobacco thrips (*Thrips tabaci* lind) is a common pest of cotton.

In addition to cotton, it also damages tobacco, onions, cabbage, and potatoes. Tobacco thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lind) migrate to weeds and sedges in March, then to cotton lawns. In the implementation of measures to combat tobacco thrips in cotton, based on the analysis of their bioecological characteristics, the economically dangerous amount of the pest is determined.

Implementation of the integrated control system is considered to be of great practical and theoretical importance in increasing the productivity of agricultural plants, including cotton. Methods and materials. Based on the analysis of the conducted experiments, the development and damage of tobacco thrips in different varieties of cotton was studied. The most dangerous period in the fight against tobacco thrips in cotton is considered to be the period from the germination of cotton until the cotton enters the full boll. Carrying out the control measures against tobacco thrips during these periods will save the plant yield and high-quality harvest makes it possible to get In order to study the dynamics of biological development of tobacco thrips in cotton, the damage it causes, and the scientific basis of carrying out control measures, it was conducted based on the methods of Sh.T. Khojayev [3]. Selection of research samples, placement of options, randomization method, biological effectiveness of drugs was determined using the Abbot (1925) formula. The statistical analysis of the obtained data was carried out using the method of B.D. Dospekhov [2].

Research results.

In our research conducted in the conditions of meadow-swamp soils of the PSUYEAITI experimental site located in Kuva district, Fergana region, during the growing season, Confedor

20% k.em., Mospilan 20% n.kuk, Benzophosphate 30% were used against tobacco thrips in Goza. n.cook was used against tobacco thrips

Table 1

Biological effectiveness of insecticides against tobacco thrips in cotton.

Device name	Expenditure		Since the pest has been treated		
	norm		then number		
	Prepa kg/ha	rat Working solution l/ha	7	14	21
			Biological efficiency	Biological efficiency	Biological efficiency
Confidor 20% k.em.	0,1	300	93,8	96,6	95,6
Mospilan 20% n.kuk.	0,2	300	83,5	89,6	76,0
Benzophosphate 30% n. kuk. (template)	3,0	300	66,4	76,2	73,8
Control (unprocessed)	-	-	-	-	-

It is known from the experimental analysis that when treated with Konfidor at 0.1 kg/ha per hectare, the biological efficiency of the drug on the 7th day of the experiment was 93.8%, after 14 days the biological efficiency of the drug was 96.6%, on the 21st day of treatment the biological efficiency was 95.6% formed 20% of Mospilan against tobacco thrips. The biological efficiency of the drug was 83.5% on the 7th day of treatment at the rate of 0.2 kg/ha, 89.6% on the 14th day, and 76% on the 21st day of treatment. Konfidor and Mospilan as a template ariant. Benzophosphate 30% n.kuk. was obtained and applied at the rate of 3 kg/ha, and the biological efficiency of the drug was 66.4% on the 7th day of treatment, and 76.2% on the 14th day of treatment. At the end of the experiment, the biological efficiency was 73%. Among the insecticides used against tobacco thrips in cotton during the conducted research, Konfidor 20% k.em. It was noted that the highest biological efficiency, i.e. 96.6%, can be achieved on the 14th day of treatment when applied in a ratio of 0.1 l/ha.

Conclusion, suggestions and recommendations.

1. Tobacco thrips overwinters mainly in fields planted with weeds and grain. It gives 7-8 generations in the first year, and its damage is especially noticeable in the first decade of May-June. 2. Tobacco thrips causes economic damage to cotton, tobacco and vegetable crops. It especially damages late-planted cottons left over from the plant. 3. Confidor 20% k.em. the highest (96.6%) biological efficiency can be achieved by using the drug in a ratio of 0.1 l/ha.

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